

Deliverable 6.1: Communication Toolkit

GEMSTONE

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D6.1 Communication Toolkit

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The first deliverable of the GEMSTONE Project, D.6.1 Communication Toolkit, provides information on how the brand identity and the first communication tools have been set up. As a coordinator, Acıbadem University (ACU) is the leader in planning and executing the project communication activities.

The major objective of the deliverable, **D6.1 Communication toolkit**, is to provide the main communication tools for the visibility of the project activities and their results, such as project websites, logos, flyers and social media channels. The tools have been designed with harmonized characteristics, reflecting the project's brand identity.

Structuring the communication toolkit is important to develop the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) including communication activities (D6.2 and 6.4)

1. OBJECTIVES, SCOPE AND CONTENT OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable composes of two major parts. Firstly, the Communication toolkit explains the graphical identity of GEMSTONE through the notion behind the outputs and the templates for visibility tools, such as the flyers, and researchers' catalogue. The second part, Media covers the website tree and its contents, social media channels and brand identity rules.

The major aim of the communication tools is to improve the visibility of the project activities, there are **eight objectives of the communication activities below**.

Objectives of communication activities

- Actively engaging with the project partners, all the researchers and the administrative staff in the GEMSTONE while creating the content of communication tools;
- Generating standard templates to improve the visibility of research outputs of GEMSTONE;
- Raising the awareness of stakeholders and potential future actors within the European innovation ecosystem, especially in Balkan countries, concerning the project activities in different contexts;
- Interact with similar projects funded by European Commission;
- Providing an attractive research group profile to have contact with promising early career researchers in neuroscience;
- Creating a best practice in capacity building in research management to attract other universities through open innovation and open science perspective;
- Generating physical and online forms of presentation tools for the project activities to reach the general public.

This deliverable provides information on how the project brand identity has been created, and how the first communication tools, including the project logo, website, flyer and social media channels, have been set up.

2. COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT

2.1 Graphic Identity

In order to present the partnership characterisation of GEMSTONE and realize the objectives of the communication strategy, a new brand identity has been created. We thought of GEMSTONE as a person to reflect the solid features of project motivation. Through brainstorming in a team member on the persona of GEMSTONE, we become able to visualize the brand identity and integrate our common culture into the general templates and all communication contents. Creating a coherent design helps to internalize the identified cultural features. Therefore, we determined the **brand personality of GEMSTONE as follows: female, inclusive, has a collective mind, excited, innovative, and takes action under the light of science.**

The motto of GEMSTONE is expressed as *“Excellence in Neuroscience!”*

The brand book includes the different versions of the logo, colour scale, and logo sizes as **Annex1: GEMSTONE Brand Identity.**

With this logo, we would like to reflect our **collaboration to reach excellence in neuroscience.** The font of GEMSTONE is preferred based on being smooth to reflect a compatible character of our partnership (**open to new collaborations**). For practical reasons, we think that the font displays a soft and compatible form on the web, as well. While the brain figure characterizes the major research field of the project, the **colours inside cover the partners' logo colours.** Also, the **sharp lines of the brain figure evoke a stone.** The extent of the brain figure expresses the bunch of colours in the brain (partners and fields of research). **The background colour of the logo matches the colours of the EU and the partners, as well. The letter "o" of GEMSTONE reflects harmonization in the collaboration.** The logo is adapted to white background and the designer set all the versions needed for dissemination (social media channels, posters, etc.). The **letter "o"** in the GEMSTONE logo is explained in Annex 1 as another active symbol in the main logo of GEMSTONE. In collaboration activities and the networking templates, we plan to use this image rather than the brain image.

Flyer

The project flyer provides the key information about the project in a concise and engaging message. The flyer was designed as a general-purpose communication tool, targeting different audience groups, including non-specialized ones.

A six-fold, 21,0 x 29,7 cm format has been selected for the flyer.

The flyer was developed by ACU using the project visual identity already developed. Its graphical elements are consistent with the visual language used for the website.

The six pages of the folded flyer are dedicated respectively to 1. Cover Page with title and the partner's logo 2-3-4-5. Project Goals and main elements of the project 6. The back cover with information about the social media channels of the project, a QR code pointing to the website and the acknowledgement of funding.

The flyer will be printed and distributed to the consortium members. It will also be downloadable from the project website in electronic format.

See **Annex II for a PDF version of the flyer.**

Templates

Under a joint brand identity, it is purposed to reach the target audiences effectively with the project activities' via professionally crafted materials. Therefore, as it is proposed in the application, a member of the training services at ACU-UZEM is selected as the Social Media Specialist in Secretariat Board, Ezgi Karatepe. She has the technical skills to integrate the brand identity into communication formats which will be used in social media channels, physical activities, and the website of the project.

To have a consistent form of brand message, we used the same colours and typefaces in all templates and communication materials. All the external communication templates are designed in Canva professional accounts belonging to ACU (see Figures 1, 2 and 3).

The formats for external communication are GEMSTONE Research Catalogue, GEMSTONE Research Group Identification for Researchers' Video Profiles, Social Media Postcards, Social Media Video Postcards, Flyers, Press releases, Brochure, Roll-up, and the Annual Newsletter.

Some examples of how the brand identity has been incorporated into the communication formats are reported below:

Figure 1: Press release prepared before the Kick-off meeting

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Figure 2: Name Tag Template (used in 1st Training Workshop)

Figure 3: GEMSTONE Researchers Catalogue, to be used in networking and brokerage events

2.2 Media

The website of GEMSTONE

The project website has been created and it is available at the following link:
<http://www.gemstoneproject.eu/>

Figure 4: Website of GEMSTONE (Main Page)

GEMSTONE's website opens with a spinning brain animation (Figure 4). This animation's background and brain image is selected from the GEMSTONE brand colour scale. When you move down from the main screen, four main headings of the web tree become apparent. These four main topics are; "About GEMSTONE", "Consortium", "Research", and "Capacity Building".

On the page "About GEMSTONE", the summary and general objectives of the project were mentioned, while on the "Consortium" page, the list of the partners and their roles in the project is provided.

Under the title of "Research", the tasks and objectives planned to be reached in the WP2 are listed. This title also covers the WP3, as the mobility of researchers and related activities for improving the

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researchers' profiles are carried out in parallel with the research activities. In this section, we will publish updates (such as images and content) that may attract researchers working in neuroscience.

In the “Capacity Building” section, the focus is on WP4 and WP5, again adhering to the content of the project. On this page, we will publish updates related to capacity-building activities in research management, as well as updates in activities related to network development, presenting new projects, and advances in corporate steps in research management.

Social media channels

During the kick-off meeting, the consortium partners discussed on which social media platform GEMSTONE should have been present, taking into account the science communication experiences of the neuroscience field. First of all, we created a LinkedIn account (GEMSTONE Twinning, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/gemstone-twinning-project/>), which has professional business interactions and is mostly used by the industrial network. Also, in recent years, many researchers have a LinkedIn profile to disseminate their articles and project. All posts are sent by tagging partners.

Three months after its creation, the LinkedIn account has already 267 followers.

A Twitter account has been therefore created for the project (gemstone.twinning, https://twitter.com/Gemstone_EU) Moreover, an Instagram account has been created for the project (gemstone.twinning, <https://www.instagram.com/gemstone.twinning/>). The reason for choosing the Instagram platform is that it is a medium where we estimate that early career researchers and PhD candidates spend more time than on other platforms. In addition, we think that Instagram will enable us to reach large public audiences who follow more tags, thanks to short videos and stories. In addition, the Instagram account of the ACU Neuroscience Doctorate Program is followed and actively used. We believe that GEMSTONE's interaction with the followers of this account will be stronger.

A GEMSTONE Social Media Calendar has been created, to better manage the social media accounts. Posts will be published on: **special days and annual celebrations, scientific publications of researchers written as popular science news, announcements, events organised by the GEMSTONE partners and news from the project activities.**

Social media hashtags are the same as with the project keywords:

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#Gemstone.twinning #DevelopmentalNeurobiology #Neurobiology, #NeurologicalDisorders,
#AlzheimerDisease, #HuntingtonDisease, #ParkinsonDisease, #AnimalBiotechnology,
#Neuropharmacology.

The media appearance is the most important aspect of communication management. The Project Manager is responsible to contact the national and international media channels (**national science magazines, newspapers, popular science writers, etc.**) to improve the visibility of the project.

REFERENCE

https://rea.ec.europa.eu/news/tackling-gender-equality-research-and-innovation-2022-03-07_en

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

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Brand Identity

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Using the Logo

Logo Variations

GEMSTONE logo;

When applied on a photographic background, a dark blue or white version should be used to provide the highest contrast with the ground.

Use on Photography

Logo on white background

Symbol Usage

Logo on dark blue background

Brand Colours

The main color tones are as follows.

C	100	R	35
M	100	G	30
Y	20	B	96
K	30		#231E60

C	0	R	255
M	0	G	255
Y	0	B	255
K	0		#FFFFFF

	C 81	M 40	Y 0	K 0
	R 35	G 30	B 96	#1C83C6
	C 58	M 58	Y 12	K 0
	R 124	G 115	B 165	#7C73A5
	C 1	M 95	Y 7	K 0
	R 234	G 41	B 136	#EA2988
	C 0	M 74	Y 42	K 0
	R 241	G 105	B 116	#F16974
	C 3	M 27	Y 78	K 0
	R 245	G 189	B 83	#F5BD53

Logo Sizes

The GEMSTONE logo should be the highlight of any app. In printed versions, the logo should never be used smaller than 3 cm horizontally. In web or smartphone applications, it should not go below 200 pixels horizontally.

PRINTED

3 cm

DIGITAL

200 px

Logo Clear Space

Do not do this

Excellence in Neuroscience

GEMSTONE

Genetically Engineering
Experimental Models:
Enhancement of Scientific
and Technological excellence
and innovation potential to
study Neurodevelopmental
diseases

CONTACT

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İstanbul, Türkiye

The GEMSTONE is a Twinning project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101078981.

RESEARCH

GEMSTONE will shed light on the the neurodevelopment of deep cortical layer in pathological conditions such as absence epilepsy and the possibility that the layer 6b cortical circuit could be exploited in the management on absence epilepsy.

GEMSTONE presents the first research to increase the knowledge of cortical neurodevelopment in absence seizure generation.

GEMSTONE provides the first comprehensive dataset for a novel therapeutic intervention for absence epilepsy through the modulation deep cortical layer on specific cellular level.

COLLABORATION

GEMSTONE will strengthen collaboration with and capitalizing on knowledge transfer from one high-ranking foreign European academic institution (ULUND) and one non-profit organisation (ICONS).

CAPACITY BUILDING

GEMSTONE will create opportunities for bilateral exchange of scientific knowledge and technical skills and training opportunities for early-career researchers in hard and soft skills.

The staff of ACU research support services will improve their capacity to support researchers in submitting successful grant applications, attracting funds, communication research results and translating them to clinics and/or in commercial products.

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT

GEMSTONE will increase ACU researchers' scientific profiles and ACU research management, administration and communication capacities, the project will decrease the disparities among ACU and the top-class leading counterparts at the European level.

WHAT IS THE GOAL OF GEMSTONE?

GEMSTONE will advance Acibadem University (ACU)'s scientific research and innovative capacity in strategic areas of gene engineering technologies and neuroscience with a focus on the neurodevelopmental aspects of brain disorders, such as Parkinson's disease and epilepsy.

VISIBILITY

GEMSTONE will increase the visibility of the project results and partners in the global neuroscience community

NETWORKING

GEMSTONE will highlight the role and commitment of the universities involved, especially ACU, as important players in this scientific area, at international level, in order to establish new collaborations and partnerships

BEST PRACTICE BOOK

Lessons learned in the performance of research and in research management and administration will be collected in a best practice book and disseminated to other universities and governments in Widening countries.